

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN APOLIPROTEIN GENE VARIANTS AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE LATE ONSET ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

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Introduction

Alzheimer's disease is a dementia form discovered in 1906 and mostly common among the elderly (Wang & Brinton, 2016). It is characterized by amyloid-beta plaques (A β) and neurofibrillary tangles (NFT). Its symptoms include progressive memory loss and cognitive function. Human Apolipoprotein is a 299-amino-acid protein associated with late onset developing risk of late onset of the disease. It is found in the blood plasma and plays a crucial role of transporting cholesterol and lipids and metabolism. ApoE helps in brain injury repair by lipid redistribution among neurons and cerebrovascular integrity and neurite outgrowth modulation.

There are three isoform variants of the gene or alleles, namely; ApoE2, ApoE3, and ApoE4. They differ with respect to two amino acids. There are therefore six possible genotypes, 2/2, 2/3, 2/4, 3/3, 3/4, 4/4 since one allele is inherited from each of the parents. ApoE-2 serves to protect against the Alzheimer's disease and is very rare (Wang & Brinton, 2016). One with ApoE-2 allele develops Alzheimer's disease later in life. The ApoE-3 is the most common but plays a neutral role in the manifestation of the disease. It neither increases nor decreases the risk of the disease. ApoE-4 increases the risk of developing the disease. A person with more ApoE-4 alleles is at higher risk of contracting the disease and is the strongest genetic risk factor. However, having the allele is not a guarantee for developing the disease as some with the allele do not develop the disease.

Non-carriers have Alzheimer's disease development frequency of 20% at 84 year's age, the heterozygous 47% at 76 year's age and homozygous at the average age of 68 years have a frequency of 91% (Wang & Brinton, 2016).

The relationship between ApoE2 and 3 and the Alzheimer's disease

ApoE2 is very a rare allele with only 5% incidence and is a protective variant against the Alzheimer's disease. A person with this allele can only develop the disease later in life. People with ApoE2 or ApoE3 alleles are less likely to develop the diseases by 40%.

Studies suggest that ApoE 2 is neuroprotective. Patients with the allele exhibit reduced disposition of amyloid-beta in the cortex and express less formation of neurofibrillary tangles. ApoE 2 protection from the Alzheimer's disease only occurs in early stages. The allele has also been connected to cognitive functions in aging (Wang & Brinton, 2016). It preserves the brain's structural integrity since it contains large hippocampal volumes and less hippocampal atrophy rate in comparison with non-carriers thereby favoring cognition and resistance to Alzheimer's disease's early-stage pathological development. Sex is a variable risk factor for the disease. Women with this allele are less protected from the disease than men.

ApoE2 brains have the most robust bioenergetic profiles in terms glucose uptake and metabolism thereby promoting its neuroprotection roles (Diniz, Butters, Albert, Dew, & Reynolds, 2013). The alleles, in comparison with both ApoE3 and ApoE4, synaptically express higher beta subunit Atp6v (a catalytic domain component) levels and is another rationale favoring cognitive function. Generally, ApoE2 brains are synaptically and bioenergetically more efficient and robust making them neuroprotective and cognitive (Wang & Brinton, 2016).

ApoE2 variant is increasingly being recognized as neuroprotective despite that fact that the underlying mechanisms have not been fully approached and understood. In this regard, it has been proposed that ApoE4 brains be therapeutically converted by structural correction, genetic modification or functional modulation into ApoE2-Like brain. The aim of this is to increase the brain's ability to fight Alzheimer's disease through a faster, safer and easier strategy. Early stages of the disease have also been associated with impaired metabolism of glucose (Wang & Brinton, 2016). Bioenergetic robustness can be increased to curb this. ApoE2 neuroprotection roles should be delegated and brain energy metabolism enhanced thereby preventing or delaying the disease's onset in an aging ApoE4 brain (Moreno, Pino, Ríos, Lopera, Ostos, Via, & Bedoya, 2017).

The relationship between the ApoE4 and the Alzheimer's disease

ApoE4 exists in only 20% of the population but has 50% incidence in Alzheimer's disease patients. This allele is associated with severe decline in cognitive functions and altered response in the treatment of the disease. Brains with ApoE4 are less efficient in A β clearance. Brains with ApoE4 alleles have been found to experience decreased cerebral metabolism of glucose, greater brain atrophy, defective hippocampal neurogenesis and impaired synaptic function. The conversion and progression of the diseases from normal ageing to MCI and finally to the Alzheimer's disease has been associated with ApoE4 and its effects are greater in the female sex than the males (Alexander, 2017).

The allele is the strongest genetic development risk factor for the disease and its presence increases risk early and late onset of the disease. Clinical and autopsy-based studies have shown

that persons with the ApoE4 are at higher risk in comparison to those with ApoE3. The more the number copies the higher the risk. ApoE2 has been demonstrated to protect against the disease.

The allele has been connected to the prevalence of the disease in and lower age onset. The frequency of development of the disease for persons with ApoE4 at the mean age of 68 is 91%, 47% at mean age of 76 and 20% at age 84 suggesting strongly that the allele increases the Alzheimer's disease development (Krstic & Knuesel, 2017).

Kanekiyo, Xu and Bu (2014) argue that ApoE plays important roles in the metabolism of amyloid-beta to form senile plaques and cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA). This is more abundant with ApoE4 in the brains of the elderly. The Allele increases the risk of the disease by initiating and speeding amyloid-beta accumulation, aggregation and disposition in the brain. The allele is also associated with CAA and its related hemorrhages detected in Alzheimer's disease. The allele combines with such diseases as atherosclerosis, type 2 diabetes peripheral vascular diseases synergistically which are Alzheimer's disease's other risk factors to increase the risk.

Conversely, the ApoE4 allele association with the disease has been proven to be weaker among African Americans and Hispanics but stronger among the Caucasians and the Japanese suggesting that the allele is only a contributing factor to the development of the disease (Alexander, 2017). Some studies have reported no direct relationship between ApoE4 and Alzheimer's disease. The presence of the ApoE4 allele has been argued to be neither necessary nor sufficient for the progression of the disease. The effects of the allele may be contributed to by other genetic and environmental factors (Michaelson, 2014).

MCI and the Alzheimer's disease

MCI is the stage between dementia and normal ageing. Patients with ApoE4 at this stage experience poor memory performance and memory decline in the middle and elderly ages. They also experience rapid decline in cognitive functions and all these are associated with ApoE4 allele (Moreno, Pino, Ríos, Lopera, Ostos, Via, & Bedoya, 2017). The allele is also associated with the MCI progression to Alzheimer's disease. These observations can act as predictive factors for the Alzheimer disease progression.

Conclusion

ApoE4 has been proven to associate with Alzheimer's disease and decline in cognition. It accelerates the rate of Alzheimer's disease conversion and progression although its effects are age dependent. This knowledge can be used to identify those who are at risk earlier (Michaelson, 2014). ApoE isoform variants maintain vascular health in different ways and defects in vascular health are roles in the development of the disease. Fully understanding the ApoE4 contribution to Alzheimer's disease pathogenesis will help in combating the disease.

References

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